

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PROCESSING AND MARKETING OF LAC IN GONDIA DISTRICT

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Abstract

The study entitled "Economic Analysis of Processing and Marketing of Lac in Gondia District" was conducted to evaluate cost structure, returns, value addition, break-even point, marketing efficiency, and constraints faced by lac processing units in the study area. Data were collected for the year 2024–2025 from two representative units, Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals and Agrawal Lac Industries as well as primary data from 75 lac growers and other marketing functionaries across three tehsils viz. Gondia, Amgaon, and Goregaon. Results indicated that capacity utilization was highest for seedlac (87.20 % and 84.00 %) and lowest for Button lac (74.00% and 67.13%). Variable costs dominated total costs (>90 %), making profitability highly sensitive to raw material prices. Vijaya achieved higher gross returns (₹21.90 crore) compared to Agrawal (₹14.05 crore) due to larger production volumes. Seedlac showed the highest benefit-cost ratio (1.42 and 1.38) and value addition (63.89% and 61.52%), whereas Button lac had the lowest break-even point (3.30 tons and 4.31 tons), indicating lower financial risk. Marketing through Channel I was more efficient (producer share 39.23%) than Channel II (38.00%). Constraints included high raw material costs, market price fluctuations, poor storage facilities, labour shortage, and high transport and electricity costs. The study concludes that seedlac is the most economically viable product, larger-scale operations increase returns, and improving marketing channels, storage infrastructure, and input price stability is crucial for sustainable growth of the lac industry.

Keywords: Lac processing, Economic analysis, Value addition, Break-even point, Marketing efficiency, Gondia district.

Introduction

Lac is a natural resin secreted mainly by Indian lac insect, *K. lacca* (Kerr) which thrives on the tender twigs of specific host trees viz., palas (*Butea monosperma*), ber (*Ziziphus mauritiana*), kusum (*Schleichera oleosa*), *Flemingia semialata*, *Ficus spp.* etc. Rangeneni and kusmi are the two strains of lac insect which are classified based on preference of the insect for specific host plants. Raw lac is the source of three valuable products i.e. resin, dye and wax. Lac cultivation is an important source of income for livelihood of the forest and sub-forest dwellers of Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, West Bengal, Maharashtra, Odisha and parts of Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat and NEH region. (Nagpure *et. al.* 2019). India is the largest producer of lac in the world and exports huge quantity of lac to different foreign countries like Germany, U.S.A, U.K. etc after fulfilment of its own demand and earns vast amount of foreign money. But sticklac, collected from lac host trees, is not directly exported and through a long process, it is converted into seedlac, shellac, button lac etc and becomes worthy of utilisation in different industries. (Gose 2018).

Objective

To work out the cost and returns of lac processing.
To estimate break even point for lac processing unit.
To study the marketing of lac and lac products.
To analyse constraints faced by lac processing unit during processing and marketing.

Materials and Methods**Area of Study:**

The Gondia district of Maharashtra State was purposively selected for the study.

Selection of Sample Units:

The sample for the study consisted of two actively operating lac processing units viz., Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals and Agrawal Lac Industries Gondia. The selection was purposive to ensure that the chosen units were representative of major lac processing activities in the region.

Sampling Technique for Marketing of Lac and Lac Products:

The present study was conducted using a multistage sampling technique to select samples for the marketing of lac and lac products in the Gondia district. In the first stage, the Gondia district was selected as the study area. In the second stage, three talukas namely Gondia, Goregaon, and Amgaon were selected randomly. In the third stage, specific villages and

marketing functionaries such as producers, wholesalers/commission agents, and retailers were selected randomly. The details of the sampling are presented in Table 1.

Period of Study:

The study was based on primary data pertained for the year 2024–2025.

Source of Data:

The primary data were collected through personal interviews conducted with owners, managers, and officials of the selected lac processing units as well as primary data from 75 lac growers and other marketing functionaries across three tehsils viz. Gondia, Amgaon, and Goregaon. Structured questionnaires and interview schedules were used for data collection.

Analytical tools for data analysis

Cost Analysis: Estimation of capital investment, fixed and variable costs, and total cost of production.

Estimation of Cost and Returns

Depreciation: Depreciation on machinery was calculated by using straight-line method taking into considerations the purchase value and expected life of machineries. Depreciation on building was taken @ 10% per annum.

Interest on fixed capital: Interest on fixed capital was calculated @ 10% per annum on the total capital investment.

Interest on working capital: Interest on working capital was calculated @ 6% per annum.

Return Analysis: Calculation of gross returns, net returns, and benefit-cost (B:C) ratios for Seedlac, Shellac, and Button lac.

Value Addition Analysis: Determination of value added over raw material costs.

Break-even Analysis: The quantity at which all costs allocated to a product are equal to all revenues from its sale is known as Break-even analysis. At quantity smaller than the break even point, there is a loss and at large quantities there is a profit. The break even point for lac processing unit was calculated with the following formula.

Computation in physical quantity,

$$\text{Break even point} = \frac{F}{P-V}$$

Computation in monetary value,

$$\text{Break even point} = \frac{F}{(1-V/P)}$$

Where,

F = Total annual fixed cost in Rs.

P = Selling price per unit in Rs.

V = Variable cost per unit in Rs.

Margin of safety: The excess of production over the BEP is called the Margin of Safety.

Computation in physical terms,

Margin of safety = Total production – BEP at quantity term

Computation in monetary terms,

Margin of safety = Gross income – BEP at monetary term

Percentage of margin of safety (%): Percentage of margin of safety was calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Percentage of margin of safety (\%)} = \frac{\text{Value of BEP}}{\text{Value of Total Output}} \times 100$$

(in physical and in monetary terms)

Marketing Analysis: Evaluation of marketing channels, marketing costs, marketing margin, price spread, producer's share in consumer rupee, and marketing efficiency indices (Conventional, Shepherd's, and Acharya & Agarwal's approaches).

Price spread: The price spread is the net price received by producer expressed in terms of percentage to consumer's price or retailer price.

$$P_S = P_C - P_R$$

Where,

P_S = Price spread

P_C = Price paid by consumer

P_R = Net price received by producer

Producer's share in consumer rupee (%): It is the percentage of net price received by the producer to the price paid by the consumer or selling price of retailer.

The producer's share in consumer rupee is expressed as:

$$= \frac{\text{Net price received by producer}}{\text{Price paid by consumer}} \times 100$$

Marketing efficiency: Marketing efficiency is the degree of market performance. It is the ratio of marketing output (satisfaction) to marketing input (cost).

Ratio of output to input method/ Conventional method: Conceptually, efficiency of any activity or process is defined as the ratio of output to input. If 'V' and 'I' are output and input respectively of the marketing system and E is the index of marketing efficiency, then,

$$E = \frac{V}{I} \times 100$$

Where,

V = Value added by marketing system

I = Marketing cost including some fair margin of middlemen

Shepherd's approach: The marketing efficiency is measured with the help of following formula given by Shepherd.

$$ME = \frac{V-1}{I}$$

Where,

V = Consumer's Price

I = Total marketing cost

Acharya and Agarwal's approach: The marketing efficiency was worked out by using modified method suggested by Acharya and Agarwal.

$$MME = \frac{FP}{MC+MM}$$

Where,

MME = Modified measures of marketing efficiency

FP = Prices received by farmer

MC = Total marketing cost

MM = Total marketing margin

Constraint Analysis: The constraints faced by lac processing unit during processing and marketing analysed using Garrett's ranking technique. The ranks given by each respondent were converted into percent position by using formula.

$$\text{Percent position} = \frac{100 \times (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given to i^{th} constraint by the j^{th} individual.

N_j = Number of constraints.

The estimated percent positions were converted into scores using Garrett's table. The mean of scores was estimated for each constraint and these means score was arranged in a descending order. The constraint with highest mean score value was considered as the most important and ranked as one and remaining mean scores have given rank in descending order.

Results and Discussion

Cost and Returns

Capital utilization of Lac Processing Units

The table 2., shows that Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals utilized 87.20% of its Seedlac capacity, 80.33% of Shellac, and 74.00% of Button lac, while Agrawal Lac Industries achieved 84.00% utilization in Seedlac, 73.33% in Shellac, and 67.13% in Button lac, indicating that Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals had relatively higher capital utilization across all products.

Capital investment of lac processing units

The capital investment in lac processing units for Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals and Agrawal Lac Industries is presented in Table 3., segregated capital investments for the main product (Seedlac) and by-products (Shellac and Button lac). The total capital investment for Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals amounted to Rs. 509.36 lakhs per year, whereas Agrawal Lac Industries invested slightly lower at Rs. 440.60 lakhs per year. The analysis suggests that Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals has a higher total capital investment, especially in core seedlac operations, reflecting a more robust infrastructure and potentially higher production efficiency. In both units, the largest portion of investment was directed towards machinery and factory buildings, highlighting the capital-intensive nature of lac processing, particularly for seedlac production.

Annual fixed cost of Lac processing units

The analysis of the annual fixed cost for lac processing units, as presented in Table 4., Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals bears a higher total annual fixed cost of Rs. 104.29 lakhs, compared to Rs. 89.51 lakhs in Agrawal Lac Industries, reflecting its larger installed capacity, greater capital investment, and more extensive infrastructure. In both units, the major contributors to fixed costs are depreciation on machinery and buildings, and interest on fixed capital, indicating the capital-intensive nature of lac processing. In conclusion, both enterprises demonstrate different cost structures based on their operational priorities. Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals follows a volume-driven, cost-efficient model, while Agrawal Lac Industries appears to adopt a technology-driven, quality-focused strategy for by-products. For improved profitability, both units should aim to optimize fixed cost utilization was Vijaya through scaling product diversification and Agrawal through enhancing capacity use of its solvent-based infrastructure.

Annual variable cost of Lac processing units

The analysis of the annual variable costs for lac processing units, as presented in Table 5., The total variable cost for Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals was significantly higher at Rs. 1580.32 lakhs, whereas Agrawal Lac Industries incurred a total of Rs. 1002.99 lakhs. This considerable difference can be largely attributed to the cost of raw materials, which remains the most dominant component of variable costs in both units.

Total Cost of lac processing units

The Table 6., presents a comparative overview of the total cost structure including fixed and variable costs for different lac products (Seedlac, Shellac, and Button lac) processed by Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals and

Agrawal Lac Industries. The total cost incurred by Vijaya for seedlac production was Rs. 768.15 lakhs, which is significantly higher than Agrawal's Rs. 518.54 lakhs. Similarly, for Shellac, Vijaya incurred Rs. 650.23 lakhs, whereas Agrawal spent Rs. 416.53 lakhs. For Button lac, the total cost was Rs. 266.23 lakhs in Vijaya and Rs. 157.43 lakhs in Agrawal's unit. These figures clearly indicate that Vijaya's processing unit operates at a larger scale and higher investment level across all product categories.

Gross Returns of Lac Products in Processing Units

The Table 7., presents the gross returns comparison for Seedlac, Shellac, and Button lac processed by Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals and Agrawal Lac Industries. Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals generates a higher total gross return of Rs. 21,90,80,650 compared to Agrawal Lac Industries' total of Rs. 14,05,63,225. This reflects Vijaya's larger production scale across all product categories, enabling it to achieve greater market presence and returns, despite the slightly lower rates for Shellac and Button lac. In contrast, Agrawal Lac Industries, with its more focused approach on quality and smaller quantities, achieves higher per-ton returns but is constrained by its lower production volume.

Economics of lac processing

The Table 8., provides a comparative analysis of the economics of lac processing across the two processing units, Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals demonstrates a superior economic outcome in lac processing, particularly in terms of absolute returns and benefit-cost ratio, primarily due to larger scale operations. On the other hand, Agrawal Lac Industries, while more cost-efficient and product-quality oriented, generates comparatively lower net returns.

Value Addition in Lac

Value addition in lac processing reflects the efficiency and profitability of transforming raw materials into marketable products. The analysis reveals that seedlac processing provides the highest value addition percentage, making it a more economically efficient product compared to shellac and button lac. This implies that while Button lac generates higher absolute gross returns, its proportionate profit margin is lower due to higher processing costs.

Break even Point

The Break even point analysis emphasizes that product choice has a substantial impact on financial sustainability in lac processing. Products with lower BEP, such as Button Lac, are advantageous as they achieve cost recovery more quickly and operate with reduced financial risk. Conversely, products with higher BEP, like seedlac, require larger production volumes and stable markets to avoid losses, making them more vulnerable to market volatility. The results suggest that lac processing units should strategically focus on high-margin, low-BEP products, while improving cost efficiency in seedlac production to enhance overall profitability.

Marketing of Lac and Lac products

Channels of Distribution

It is observed that, there were following two marketing channels identified for distribution of lac in Gondia district.

Channel-I: Producers → Commission agents cum wholesalers → processors.

Channel-II: Producers → Retailers → Commission agents cum wholesalers → processors → Export.

Channels wise sale of Lac

The analysis of Table 11., reveals that the majority of lac sales in Gondia district are carried out through Channel I. A total of 49 producers utilized this channel, selling 54.40 quintals of lac at an average price of Rs. 49,109 per quintal. This clearly shows that Channel I is the most preferred route for marketing lac, as it allows producers to sell larger

quantities directly to commission agents and wholesalers with minimal intermediaries.

Marketing Cost incurred by marketing functionaries

The analysis from Table 12., indicates that marketing lac through Channel I is more favourable for lac growers, as it involves fewer intermediaries and ensures faster payment and better price realization despite higher direct expenses. Channel II lowers initial costs for producers but allows middlemen to capture a larger share of profits, reducing grower income.

Channel wise price spread of Lac and Lac Products:

The analysis from Table 13., it can be concluded that Channel I is more efficient and beneficial for lac producers as it involves fewer intermediaries, lower marketing costs, and provides a higher producer's share in the final price. Channel II, while providing a slightly higher net price to producers, results in greater marketing costs and margins for intermediaries, leading to a wider price spread. Strengthening shorter marketing channels, reducing unnecessary intermediaries, and promoting direct sales between producers and processors can help improve lac growers' income and overall marketing efficiency of lac in Gondia district.

Marketing efficiency

The data in Table 14., shows that the consumer's purchase price of lac was slightly higher in Channel II (Rs. 1,25,500 per quintal) compared to Channel I (Rs. 1,21,000 per quintal). Similarly, the total marketing cost was also higher in Channel II (Rs. 16,711) than in Channel I (Rs. 13,545). Despite these additional costs, intermediaries in Channel II retained a higher total marketing margin (Rs. 61,099) compared to Channel I (Rs. 59,980), indicating that producers benefit less when the marketing chain becomes longer and involves more intermediaries. The index of marketing efficiency calculated using different approaches shows that Channel I is more efficient than Channel II. Under the conventional approach, marketing efficiency was 5.43 for Channel I compared to 4.66 for Channel II. Using Shepherd's approach, efficiency was higher for Channel I (7.93) than Channel II (6.51). Similarly, the Acharya and Agarwal method showed a slight advantage for Channel I (1.64) over Channel II (1.61). These values indicate that Channel I, with fewer intermediaries, lower costs, and better price realization for producers, provides a more efficient marketing system for lac.

Constraints faced by lac processing unit during processing and marketing

The Table 15., presents the key constraints faced by lac processing units during processing and marketing activities. The most critical problem identified was the high cost of raw materials, with the highest average score of 78 and ranked first. This indicates that processors face major financial pressure due to expensive raw lac, which directly reduces their profit margins. The second most serious issue was price variation in the market (average score 66), where frequent fluctuations in lac prices create uncertainty in planning, processing, and selling activities.

Conclusions

The study on "Economic Analysis of Processing and Marketing of Lac in Gondia District", revealed that seedlac is the most economically viable product, offering the highest value addition and benefit-cost ratio, while Button lac, though less profitable, involves lower financial risk due to its lower break-even point. Large-scale processing units like Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals achieved higher profitability compared to smaller units, highlighting the importance of economies of scale. The cost structure showed that variable costs, especially raw material prices, dominated total expenses, making profitability highly sensitive to price fluctuations. In terms of marketing, Channel I (Producers → Wholesalers → Processors) was more efficient than Channel II, as it ensured a higher producer's share and reduced intermediary margins. However, the industry continues to face significant challenges, including high raw

material costs, frequent market price variations, inadequate storage facilities, labour shortages, and rising transport and electricity expenses.

References

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Table 1.: Sample size for marketing of lac and lac products in Gondia district

Marketing Functionaries	Sample size for lac and lac products marketing in Gondia district			Total
	Gondia	Amgaon	Goregaon	
Producers	25	25	25	75
Retailers	5	4	5	14
Commision agent cum Wholesalers	4	2	2	08
Processors	2	-	-	02
Exporter	1	-	-	01
Total	37	31	32	100

Table 2.: Capital utilization of Lac Processing units

(Value in ton)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Name of Unit					
		Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals			Agrawal Lac Industries		
		Seedlac	Shellac	Button lac	Seedlac	Shellac	Button lac
1	Capacity of production per month in ton	8.72	4.82	1.85	6.05	3.08	1.00
2	Actual production in year	87.20 (87.20)	48.20 (80.33)	18.50 (74.00)	58.80 (84.00)	30.80 (73.33)	10.07 (67.13)
3	Capacity of unit per year in ton	100.00 (100.00)	60.00 (100.00)	25.00 (100.00)	70.00 (100.00)	42.00 (100.00)	15.00 (100.00)

(Figures in parentheses indicates percentage to the total quantity processed)

Table 3.: Capital investment of lac processing units

(Rs/Year, In lakhs)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Name of Unit			
		Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals		Agrawal Lac Industries	
A) Main Product (Seedlac)		Seedlac		Seedlac	
1	Machinery	215.50		161.55	
2	Factory building and other structure	135.00		120.00	
3	Investment on land	12.00		8.00	
4	Furniture and other appliances	9.19		6.94	
5	Electricity installation charges	2.50		1.50	
Sub Total (A)		374.19		298.00	
B) By-products (Shellac, Button lac)		Shellac	Button lac	Shellac	Button lac
1	Machinery	70.30	50.87	80.16	53.33
2	Furniture and other appliances	7.20	6.80	5.45	3.66
Total		77.50	57.67	85.61	56.99
Sub Total (B)		135.17		142.60	
Total (A+B)		509.36		440.60	

Table 4.: Annual fixed cost of Lac processing units

(Rs/Year, In lakhs)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Name of Unit			
		Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals		Agrawal Lac Industries	
A) Main Product (Seedlac)		Seedlac		Seedlac	
1	Depreciation on machinery @10%	21.55		16.15	
2	Depreciation on building @10%	13.50		12.00	
3	Depreciation on furniture @5%	0.45		0.34	
4	Taxes and insurance	1.01		0.60	
5	Permanent employee's salary	1.90		1.10	
6	Interest on fixed capital @10%	37.41		29.80	
Sub Total (A)		75.84		60.00	
B) By-products (Shellac, Button lac)		Shellac	Button lac	Shellac	Button lac
1	Depreciation on machinery @10%	7.03	5.08	8.01	5.33
2	Taxes and insurance	0.80	0.65	0.40	0.65
3	Permanent employee's salary	0.75	0.62	0.50	0.35
4	Interest on fixed capital @10%	7.75	5.76	8.56	5.69
Total		16.33	12.12	17.47	12.03
Sub Total (B)		28.45		29.51	
Total (A+B)		104.29		89.51	

Table 5.: Annual Variable Cost of Lac Processing units

(Rs/Year, In lakhs)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Name of Unit			
		Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals		Agrawal Lac Industries	
A) Main Product (Seedlac)		Seedlac		Seedlac	
1	Cost of raw materials	648.00		459.00	
2	Casual labour charges	2.44		1.97	
3	Repair and maintenance	0.45		0.25	
4	Energy, oil charges	1.92		1.21	
5	Postage, stationery and telephone, wifi charges	0.30		0.15	
6	Interest on working capital @ 6%	39.18		25.95	
Sub Total (A)		692.31		458.54	
B) Byproducts (shellac, button lac)		Shellac	Button lac	Shellac	Button lac
1	Cost of raw materials	630.04	215.00	395.95	142.45
2	Casual labour charges	1.50	1.21	1.30	1.01
3	Repair and maintenance	0.80	0.50	0.60	0.40
4	Energy, oil charges	1.56	1.40	1.20	1.54
5	Interest on working capital @ 6%	38.03	15.24	23.94	8.72
Total		633.90	254.11	399.05	145.40
Sub Total (B)		888.01		544.45	
Total (A+B)		1580.32		1002.99	

Table 6.: Total cost incurred by lac processing units

(Rs/Year, In lakhs)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Products	Name of Unit	
			Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals	Agrawal Lac Industries
1	Fixed cost	Seedlac	75.84 (9.87)	60.00 (11.58)
		Shellac	16.33 (2.51)	17.47 (4.19)
		Button lac	12.12	12.03

			(4.55)	(7.64)
2	Variable cost	Seedlac	692.31 (90.12)	458.54 (88.42)
		Shellac	633.90 (97.48)	399.05 (95.80)
		Button lac	254.11 (95.44)	145.40 (92.35)
Total cost incurred by the unit	Seedlac	768.15 (100.00)	518.54 (100.00)	
	Shellac	650.23 (100.00)	416.53 (100.00)	
	Button lac	266.23 (100.00)	157.43 (100.00)	

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total)

Table 7.: Comparative Gross Returns of Lac Products in Processing Units

(Rs. /unit)

Sr. No	Products	Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals			Agrawal Lac Industries		
		Qt. in ton	Rate (Rs/ton)	Total (Rs)	Qt. in ton	Rate (Rs/ton)	Total (Rs)
1	Seedlac	87.20	12,50,200	10,90,17,440	58.80	12,20,500	7,17,65,400
2	Shellac	48.20	16,15,550	7,78,69,510	30.80	16,25,550	5,00,66,940
3	Button lac	18.50	17,40,200	3,21,93,700	10.70	17,50,550	1,87,30,885
	Total	154		21,90,80,650	100		14,05,63,225

Table 8.: Economics of lac processing

(Rs. /unit)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Products	Name of Unit			
			Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals		Agrawal Lac Industries	
			Rs/year	Value (Rs/ton)	Rs/year	Value (Rs/ton)
1	Gross Return (Rs)	Seedlac	10,90,17,440	12,50,200	7,17,65,400	12,20,500
		Shellac	7,78,69,510	16,15,550	5,00,66,940	16,25,550
		Button lac	3,21,93,700	17,40,200	1,87,30,885	17,50,550
2	Total cost incurred by lac processing unit (Rs)	Seedlac	7,68,15,406	8,80,910	5,18,54,506	8,81,879
		Shellac	6,50,23,000	13,49,024	4,16,53,230	13,52,377
		Button lac	2,66,23,470	14,39,106	1,57,43,600	14,71,364
3	Net Return (Rs)	Seedlac	3,22,02,034	3,69,289	1,99,10,893	3,38,620
		Shellac	1,28,46,510	2,66,525	84,13,710	2,73,172
		Button lac	55,70,230	3,01,093	29,87,285	2,79,185
4	Benefit cost ratio	Seedlac		1.42		1.38
		Shellac		1.20		1.20
		Button lac		1.21		1.19

Table 9.: Value addition in lac

(Rs/ton)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Name of Unit					
		Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals			Agrawal Lac Industries		
		Seedlac	Shellac	Button lac	Seedlac	Shellac	Button lac
1	Cost of raw material	7,43,119	13,07,136	13,56,756	7,29,591	12,85,568	13,31,317
2	Cost of processing	8,80,910	13,49,024	14,39,106	8,81,879	13,52,377	14,71,364
3	Gross returns (per ton)	12,50,200	16,15,550	17,40,200	12,20,500	16,25,550	17,50,550
4	Value addition	3,69,289	2,66,525	3,01,093	3,38,620	2,73,172	2,79,185
5	% of value addition in cost of raw material	49.69	20.38	22.19	46.41	21.24	20.97

Table 10.: Break even point analysis of lac processing unit

Sr. No.	Particulars	Name of Unit					
		Vijaya Shellac and Chemicals			Agrawal Lac Industries		
		Seedlac	Shellac	Button lac	Seedlac	Shellac	Button lac
1	Actual quantity processed per year in ton	87.20	48.20	18.50	58.80	30.80	10.70
2	Annual fixed cost (Rs) (F)	75,84,050	16,33,000	12,12,470	60,00,295	17,47,710	12,03,500
3	Selling price per ton (Rs) (P)	12,50,200	16,15,550	17,40,200	12,20,500	16,25,550	17,50,550
4	Variable cost per ton (Rs) (V)	7,93,937	13,15,145	13,73,567	7,79,833	12,95,633	14,71,364
5	Break even point (tons)	16.62	5.43	3.30	13.61	5.29	4.31
	Margin of safety in physical terms	70.57	42.76	15.19	45.18	25.50	6.38
	% of margin of safety	19.06	11.27	17.87	23.15	17.19	40.28
6	Break even point (Rs)	2,07,80,977	87,82,127	57,54,919	1,66,18,827	86,11,246	75,46,189
	Margin of safety in monetary terms	8,82,36,462	6,90,87,382	2,64,38,780	5,51,46,572	4,14,55,693	1,11,84,695
	% of margin of safety	19.06	11.27	17.87	23.15	17.19	40.28

Table 11.: Channel wise sale of lac in Gondia District

Sr. No.	Place (Tehsil)	Channels	Channels wise distribution of lac		
			Lac growers (Producers)	Quantity in (qtl)	Average price (Rs.)
1	Gondia	I	16	19.60 (36.02)	49593
		II	9	5.90 (32.96)	48055
2	Amgaon	I	15	17.40 (31.98)	48866
		II	10	7.30 (40.78)	48500
3	Goregaon	I	18	17.40 (31.98)	48866
		II	7	4.70 (26.25)	47857
Total		I	49	54.40 (100.00)	49109
		II	26	17.90 (100.00)	48137

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total)

Table 12.: Channel wise Cost of Marketing of Lac and Lac Products

Sr. No.	Particulars	(Rs/Qtl.)	
		Channel I	Channel II
A	Marketing cost of Producers		
1	Bag	102	105
2	Hamali charges	240	110
3	Transportation charges	790	-
4	Storage Moisture losses	350	140
5	Depreciation of weighing balance, gunny bag, etc	48	45
6	Miscellaneous	105	48
	Total marketing cost of producers	1635	448
	Selling price of Producers	49109	48138
B	Marketing cost of Retailers		
1	Bag	-	107
2	Hamali charges	-	460
3	Transportation charges	-	820
4	Storage Moisture losses	-	1340
5	Labour Charges	-	480
6	Shop rent	-	290

7	Depreciation of weighing balance, gunny bag,etc	-	148
8	Other expenses	-	115
	Total marketing cost of Retailers	-	3760
	Selling price of Retailers	-	54000
	Market margin of Retailers	-	2102
C	Marketing cost of Commission agents cum Wholesalers		
1	Bag	110	108
2	Hamali charges	430	470
3	Transportation charges	685	760
4	Storage Moisture losses	1355	1320
5	Labour Charges	560	440
6	Shop rent	320	280
7	Depreciation of weighing balance, gunny bag,etc	120	95
8	Other expenses	110	110
	Total marketing cost of Commission agents cum Wholesalers	3690	3583
	Selling price of Commission agents cum Wholesalers	65000	62550
	Market margin of Commission agents cum Wholesalers	12201	4467
D	Marketing cost of Processors		
1	Packing charges	1250	1150
2	Hamali charges	850	1210
3	Transportation charges	1750	1760
4	Storage Moisture losses	1550	1520
5	Labour Charges	1230	1550
6	Shop rent	450	470
7	Depreciation of weighing balance, gunny bag,etc	120	110
8	Other expenses	1020	1150
	Total marketing cost of Processors	8220	8920
	Selling price of Processors	121000	125500
	Market margin of Processors	50455	54029
E	Total marketing cost	13545	16711
F	Total market margin	59980	61099

Table 13.: Channel wise Price Spread of Lac and Lac Products

(Rs/Qtl.)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Total cost	
		Channel I	Channel II
1	Net price received by Lac Producer	47474 (32.74)	47689 (38.15)
2	Total marketing cost incurred by Producers, Retailers, Wholesalers, Processors	13545 (9.34)	16411 (13.12)
3	Total market margin of Retailers, Wholesalers, Processors	59980 (57.91)	61099 (48.71)
4	Purchase price of consumer	121000 (100.00)	125500 (100.00)
5	Price Spread	73526	77811
6	Processor's share in consumer's rupee (%)	39.23	38.00

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total)

Table 14.: Channel wise Marketing efficiency of Lac and Lac Products

Sr. No.	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II
1	Consumer's purchase price	121000	125500
2	Total marketing cost	13545	16711
3	Total marketing margin	59980	61099
4	Index of Marketing Efficiency		
i.	Conventional approach	5.43	4.66
ii.	Shepherd's approach	7.93	6.51
iii.	Acharya And Agarwal's approach	1.64	1.61

(Rs. /Qtl.)

Table 15.: Constraints faced by lac processing unit during processing and marketing

Sr. No.	Problems	Percent position	Garret value	Average Score	Rank
1	High cost of raw materials	7.14	78	78.00	I
2	Labour shortage	21.43	66	47.00	IV
3	High cost of transport	35.71	58	43.00	V
4	High Electricity charges	50.00	50	42.50	VI
5	Product Awareness	64.29	43	22.00	VII
6	Problem in storage facilities	78.57	35	53.00	III
7	Problem of price variation in market	92.85	22	66.00	II